

Developmental maturation of presynaptic ribbon numbers in chicken basilar-papilla hair cells and its perturbation by long-term overexpression of Wnt9a

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Funding information

Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, Grant/Award Numbers: KO 1143/15-1, SI 823/3-1

Abstract

The avian basilar papilla is a valuable model system for exploring the developmental determination and differentiation of sensory hair cells and their innervation. In the mature basilar papilla, hair cells form a well-known continuum between two extreme types—tall and short hair cells—that differ strikingly in their innervation. Previous work identified Wnt9a as a crucial factor in this differentiation. Here, we quantified the number and volume of immunolabelled presynaptic ribbons in tall and short hair cells of chickens, from developmental stages shortly after ribbons first appear to the mature posthatching condition. Two longitudinal locations were sampled, responding to best frequencies of approximately 1 kHz and approximately 5.5 kHz when mature. We found significant reductions of ribbon number during normal development in the tall-hair-cell domains, but stable, low numbers in the short-hair-cell domains. Exposing developing hair cells to continuous, excessive Wnt9a levels (through virus-mediated overexpression) led to transiently abnormal high numbers of ribbons and a delayed reduction of ribbon numbers at all sampled locations. Thus, (normally) short-hair-cell domains also showed tall-hair-cell like behaviour, confirming previous findings (Munnamalai et al., 2017). However, at 3 weeks posthatching, ribbon numbers had decreased to the location-specific typical values of control hair cells at all sampled locations. Furthermore, as shown previously, mature hair cells at the basal, high-frequency location harboured larger ribbons than more apically located hair cells. This was true for both normal and Wnt9a-overexposed basilar papillae.

KEYWORDS

auditory, avian, bird, cochlea, inner ear, short hair cell, tall hair cell

1 | INTRODUCTION

The auditory epithelium of vertebrates is composed of different types of sensory cells (Manley, 2017). Similar to the mammalian organ of Corti, the auditory organ of birds, the basilar papilla (BP), exhibits two different hair-cell types:

tall hair cells (THC) and short hair cells (SHC). Despite their independent evolution, clear functional analogies are recognized between those hair cell types of birds and mammals (reviewed, e.g., in Köppl, 2011). The THC of birds, similar to mammalian inner hair cells (IHC), provide the afferent input to the central auditory system, via specialized

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ribbon synapses with afferent neurones. The SHC of birds are devoid of afferent connections but receive prominent efferent innervation. Similar to mammalian outer hair cells (OHC), they appear to act as amplifiers or modulators of cochlear mechanics. Candidate mechanisms by which these two cell types are established during development, in both mammals and birds, were recently reviewed by Munnamalai and Fekete (2020).

In the chicken's BP, THC and SHC grade into each other, both along the tonotopic (longitudinal) axis and the cross-sectional dimension (from neural to abneural) of this sensory organ. At the organ's apex (in the chicken, approximately 65 to 100% distance from the basal end) and along almost all the neural edge, hair cells have a THC phenotype, whereas at the very basal end and abneurally, hair cells have a SHC phenotype (Fischer, 1992; Hirokawa, 1978b). Mature THC and SHC differ in their cell-body shape and in their innervation by afferent and efferent synaptic terminals. THC are defined as being taller than wide, that is, their soma height/width ratio is greater than 1 (Tanaka & Smith, 1978). Furthermore, THC are typically innervated by several afferents and small efferents (Fischer, 1992; Hirokawa, 1978b) and contain a larger number of presynaptic ribbons than SHC (Martinez-Dunst et al., 1997). In contrast to this, SHC somata are wider than tall, with a height/width ratio below 1 (Tanaka & Smith, 1978). SHC are innervated only by large efferent terminals (Fischer, 1992; Hirokawa, 1978b) and typically contain fewer presynaptic ribbons than THC, or none at all (Martinez-Dunst et al., 1997). Beside the chicken, the same basic gradients in hair-cell morphology have also been observed in all other avian species investigated: pigeon (Takasaka & Smith, 1971), starling (*Sturnus vulgaris*, Fischer et al., 1992), duck (*Anas platyrhynchos*; Chandler, 1984), emu (*Dromaius novaehollandiae*, Fischer, 1998; Köppl et al., 1998), and barn owl (*Tyto alba*; Fischer, 1994b).

During development, hair cells from different longitudinal and cross-sectional locations of the chicken BP develop and mature at different times (Cohen & Fermin, 1978; Fermin & Cohen, 1984), similar to the mammalian organ of Corti. During mammalian inner-ear development, hair-cell differentiation occurs in a base-to-apex wave, even though the exit of cell cycle has an apex-to-base gradient (Ruben, 1967). In chickens, hair-cell differentiation follows the same developmental gradients along and across the BP, with the basal-neural region leading (Cohen & Fermin, 1978; Fermin & Cohen, 1984). This gradual hair-cell patterning concerns the shape of the hair cells and their innervation, but also the number of presynaptic ribbons they contain.

Presynaptic ribbons are found in the cytoplasm juxtaposed to the membrane of hair cells in the auditory system and also in retinal photoreceptor cells of the visual system. They consist of an electron-dense core composed of the protein RIBEYE that has two domains: a unique A domain and a

B domain (shared with, and identical to, the nuclear protein CtBP2; Schmitz et al., 2000). The electron-dense structure is surrounded by a monolayer of vesicles filled with neurotransmitter, and tethered to the ribbon core. Ribbons are attached to the presynaptic active zone and adjacent to postsynaptic densities of afferent fibers (Rutherford, 2015). In the avian BP, ribbons have also been observed located close to non-neural structures (Hirokawa, 1978a; Whitehead & Morest, 1985a), especially in future SHC (Rebillard & Pujol, 1983), but also facing efferent terminals (Tanaka & Smith, 1978). To date, there is a little agreement on when ribbon formation initiates, and how ribbon numbers change during development in the chicken BP. The first immunolabelled CtBP2 puncta have been observed as early as the eighth embryonic day (E8, of a total of 21 embryonic days in chicken; Hamburger & Hamilton, 1951) by some authors (Levic et al., 2011), while others detected them as electron-dense bodies significantly later, at E10 (Hirokawa, 1978a; Rebillard & Pujol, 1983; Whitehead & Morest, 1985a,b) or even E12 (Cohen & Fermin, 1978; Fermin & Cohen, 1984). In the stages following their initial detection, the number of ribbons was reported to increase, especially by Rebillard and Pujol (1983). Some of these ribbons were observed to lie opposite immature afferent terminals that only just contacted the hair cell. Many others, however, were not clearly associated with any postsynaptic specializations, a phenomenon commonly referred to as orphaned ribbons.

In still later stages of development (E20), there are typically almost no orphaned ribbons in THC and fewer remaining ribbons in SHC than THC (Rebillard & Pujol, 1983). While Levic and colleagues (2011) observed a continuous increase in ribbon numbers during embryogenesis and into early posthatching ages (P2), other authors described a decrease in the number of ribbons in later stages of development (Rebillard & Pujol, 1983; Whitehead & Morest, 1985b). Together with a growth in size of the afferent terminals, each typically now facing more than one ribbon, and an apparent movement of ribbons towards additional new afferent terminals, the number of orphaned ribbons also reduced at later stages (Cohen & Fermin, 1978; Hirokawa, 1978a). Importantly, in many of these classical transmission electron-microscopy studies, it remains unclear which specific location of the papilla was studied. This is highly relevant since, as explained above, hair cells at different positions of the BP develop and mature at different times. Different sample sites could, therefore, be one of the reasons for the lack of consensus between authors. The present study aims to describe more comprehensively the dynamics of ribbon development during the chicken's inner ear embryogenesis.

In contrast to the conflicting information in birds, it is generally accepted for mammals that ribbons in cochlear hair cells undergo systematic developmental changes. Increases in the number of ribbons are typically observed in both

embryonic IHC and OHC, with a marked decrease after the onset of hearing (Huang et al., 2012; Kalluri & Monges-Hernandez, 2017; Liberman & Liberman, 2016; Michanski et al., 2019; Sobkowicz et al., 1982, 1986). Furthermore, in the mammalian organ of Corti, both ribbon number and size decrease as development progresses. The developmental decrease and final size of ribbons depend on their spatial location: ribbons situated on the pillar (abneural) side of mature IHC are typically smaller than those situated on the modiolar side (Kalluri & Monges-Hernandez, 2017; Liberman et al., 2011). Nothing is currently known about the dynamics of the volume of the ribbons in the developing chicken inner ear.

The development of different hair-cell types in both the mammalian cochlea and the chicken BP requires the precisely timed activation of Notch, Wnt, and BMP signaling pathways (Munnamalai & Fekete, 2020). More specifically, the activation of the canonical Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway is influential or even required for proliferation and hair-cell formation in the developing auditory organs of chickens and mammals (Jacques et al., 2012; Munnamalai & Fekete, 2013, 2016; Stevens et al., 2003; Zak et al., 2015).

The Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway is activated by Wnt ligands binding to frizzled receptors and LPR coreceptors (LDL-receptor-related-protein) that are present on the cell's surface (Miller, 2002). Within the Wnt ligand gene family, Wnt9a (previously Wnt14), activates the canonical Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway. During inner-ear development in chickens, Wnt9a is initially expressed in the auditory primordium at E4-4.5. Shortly thereafter, by stage E5-5.5, Wnt9a expression has vanished from the future BP and its expression is confined to the adjacent nonsensory wall of the cochlear duct, forming a persistent source of Wnt9a from the neural side of the developing auditory epithelium along its entire length (Munnamalai et al., 2017; Sienknecht & Fekete, 2008, 2009). When experimentally overexpressed from an early stage (E3), Wnt9a alters the hair-cell gradient across the radial axis of the developing chicken auditory organ. It influences hair-cell fate by creating a THC-like phenotype in the abneural domain of the BP, that is, at positions where SHC are normally located. This phenotype is characterized, at E18, by having fewer or no efferent terminals, an increased number of ribbons per hair cell, and a mixture of THC and SHC physiological properties: a fast, noninactivating THC-like current, and an SHC-like inactivating current (Munnamalai et al., 2017).

In the present study, we aimed to characterize the developmental sequence of ribbon number and volume in the differentiating auditory epithelium between E12 and E18, and compare this to ears with a virus-mediated overexpression of Wnt9a. In addition to embryonic development, we extended our analysis to include posthatching day (P) 21, to assess the state of the modified phenotype in the mature ear, as a prerequisite for functional investigation.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Virus production and injection

An RCAS(A) retrovirus carrying the Wnt9a gene was produced by transfecting a DF-1 chicken fibroblast cell line (Himly et al., 1998) with an RCASBP(A) plasmid containing the full-length, open-reading frame of the chicken Wnt9a gene (CT#693, Addgene plasmid #13948; Addgene, Cambridge, MA, USA; Hartmann & Tabin, 2001). Cells were cultivated at 37°C and 5% CO₂ until virus harvest. Afterwards, the supernatant was harvested followed by concentration and titering as described previously (Morgan & Fekete, 1996; virus concentration: 3.15×10^9 cfu/mL). Specific pathogen-free fertilized White Leghorn chicken eggs (VALO BioMedia GmbH, Osterholz-Scharmbeck, Germany) were incubated at 38°C in humidified air. The eggs were windowed at E2 and staged according to Hamburger and Hamilton (1951). The right otic vesicle of the developing embryos was injected with the RCAS(A)Wnt9a retrovirus at E3. The contralateral (left) otic vesicle was left untreated to develop normally and serve as a control. The eggs were incubated until harvested at stages between E12 and E18, or until hatching. The survival rate of embryos up to E19 was 39%, but the hatching rate was extremely low (4%). Complications with the hatched chickens reduced the number of individuals available for study even further. The hatchlings were housed until P21, which was considered the mature condition (Cohen & Fermin, 1985; Fermin & Cohen, 1984; Manley et al., 1991). The distribution of the virus and the Wnt9a expression after injection were previously characterized by Munnamalai et al. (2017). All animal procedures were performed in accordance with the German Animal Welfare Act (permit number 33.19-42502-04-16/2288 by LAVES, Oldenburg, Germany).

2.2 | Tissue preparation and immunohistochemistry

Animals of most stages (E14, E16, E18, and P21) were fixed by transcardial perfusion, of 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), followed by immersion of the head in the same solution for 24 h. Embryos at E12 were decapitated and the head rapidly submerged in 4% PFA in PBS for 24 h. The cochlear duct was then dissected from the otic capsule and the BP processed for wholemount staining by removing the auditory nerve, the tegmentum vasculosum, the abneural limbus, and the lagenar macula. The dissected BP was stored at 4°C in PBS with 0.05% sodium azide added until staining was performed. For immunohistochemistry, the BP were washed in PBS with 0.2% Triton X-100 (PBS/T) and blocked in calf-serum blocking solution (10% calf serum, 0.05% sodium azide, 0.4% Triton X-100) for

30 min at room temperature, prior to incubation with the primary antibody. Anti-CtBP2 primary antibody (1:500; monoclonal mouse IgG1; BD612044; BD Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA) was diluted in blocking solution and BPs incubated in this overnight at 37°C. After washing with PBS/T, the tissue was incubated for 3 h with the secondary antibody AF568 (1:1000; goat anti-mouse IgG1; A-211241), followed by an additional wash in PBS/T. The following primary antibodies were diluted in blocking solution, in which the BP were incubated overnight at 37°C: anti-Myosin VIIa (1:400; rabbit IgG; 25-6,790; Proteus BioScience, Ramona, CA, USA), and anti-Synapsin Ia/b (1:1,000; mouse IgG2a; sc-376622; Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Inc., Dallas, TX, USA). The tissue was then washed with PBS/T to eliminate the excess of primary antibodies. Two IgG specific secondary AlexaFluor (AF) antibodies (Molecular Probes, Inc., Eugene, OR, USA) were used: AF350 (1:500; donkey anti-rabbit IgG; A-10039) and AF647 (1:500; goat anti-mouse IgG2a; A-21241). Incubations were at 37°C for 3 h followed by washes in PBS with 0.2% Triton X-100.

BP were mounted using Vectashield antifade mounting medium (Vector Laboratories, H-1000) and cover-slipped using spacers to prevent crushing.

2.3 | Microscopy and image analysis

Low-magnification bright-field images were taken and stitched together into a photomontage covering the entire BP. The length of the BPs and the locations 10 and 50% from the basal end were determined with ImageJ (National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA). High-magnification multichannel confocal image stacks of the 10 and 50% locations from the basal end of the organ were then taken, separately for neural and abneural sample areas, at each longitudinal location (overview in Figure 1A). Image stacks covering the hair-cell areas were acquired with a Leica TSC SP8 confocal microscope (Leica Microsystems CMS GmbH) using an oil-immersion objective (63×, numerical aperture 1.40) by consecutive scanning of the different fluorescent channels using 0.3–0.5 μm steps in the z -dimension and a typical pixel dimension of 60 nm (maximally 90 nm), resulting in a typical (median) voxel volume of 0.001 μm^3 . The 405, 522, and 638 nm lasers were alternatively used to excite the fluorescent antibodies, and a hybrid detector in photon-counting mode was used for detecting the emitted light. The bandwidths for each channel were calibrated to prevent crosstalk. The image stacks were later deconvolved with Huygens Essential deconvolution software (Scientific Volume Imaging B.V., Hilversum, The Netherlands) using a maximum number of iterations of 80, a signal-to-noise ratio of 10, and a quality threshold of 0.01. To establish the number and volume of ribbons, the stacks were subsequently processed using a custom 3D image analysis MATLAB 2015a procedure (The MathWorks, Inc.,

Natick, MA, USA). First, the area of interest was specified by the summation of all labeled structures in all channels. Second, the borders of typically six individual hair cells (see Supporting information Table S1 for precise sample sizes) were defined in all three dimensions (neural-abneural, apical-basal, and top-bottom) by interactively set planes. Next, the ribbons belonging to those selected cells were detected by a combination of intensity and size thresholding. Irregularly shaped elements that appeared to be two or more overlapping ribbons—assuming that a typical ribbon has a regular round or cylindrical shape—were interactively split. Figure 1B–I illustrates some examples of confocal image stacks (cropped for illustrative purposes) and three to four individual hair cells with their presynaptic ribbons extracted from each. In a minority of cases in which the definition of individual hair cell borders proved to be impossible (6 of 97 stacks), a group of 6 to 10 cells was analyzed as one bulk object, and only a mean number of ribbons per hair cell obtained (see Supporting information Table S1). Through random renaming of the image files by another person, the synapse analysis was carried out blinded regarding the specimen and location of the hair cell within the BP.

It has previously been argued that ribbon volume measurements from fluorescent immunohistochemical preparations are subject to large variations that are more related to specimen preparation and image acquisition than to biological variation. This is because the typical size of hair-cell presynaptic ribbons (200–300 nm long axis, Nouvian et al., 2006) is below the resolution of standard confocal microscopy. What is measured instead is the size of the fluorescent halo associated with antibody binding. A normalization to median volume in a given confocal image stack was, therefore, established to eliminate this artefactual variance (Lieberman et al., 2011). This precludes, however, comparisons across different image stacks that cover, for example, different spatial locations within the BP. We argue here that it is justifiable to normalize ribbon volumes across several confocal stacks if these are derived from the same BP wholemount. To minimize technical variation, individual BPs were prepared as undivided wholemounts, and all locations were imaged with the same confocal laser parameters. The raw ribbon volumes were later independently normalized relative to two different median volumes, depending on the intended comparison: (1) to the median volume in two stacks covering neural and abneural cross-sectional locations of the BP, at a given longitudinal location, and (2) to the median volume in two stacks covering the same cross-sectional location (neural or abneural) at two different longitudinal locations.

2.4 | Statistical analysis

All statistical procedures were carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics version 25 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). The

FIGURE 1 Overview of basilar papilla for general orientation, and examples of confocal images and image analysis, all from P21 control ears. The central panel A shows a schematic outline of the basilar papilla, defining the two main axes: Longitudinal (from apex to base) and cross-sectional (from neural to abneural). The four standard sample sites, at locations 50% (equivalent to 1 kHz) and 10% (equivalent to 5.5 kHz) from the basal end, are indicated as white rectangles. At each longitudinal location, two samples were taken, from the neural and the abneural edge. Arrows point to four pairs of panels, illustrating an example from each location: B, C: 50% neural, D, E: 50% abneural, F, G: 10% neural, H, I: 10% abneural. Panels B, D, F, and H each show the confocal image, with two or three immunolabels. Panels C, E, G, and I show the 3D mesh reconstructions of three to four hair cells isolated from the same confocal stack, together with the synaptic ribbons allocated to them. Note that due to the mosaic arrangement of hair cells in the avian BP, it was mostly impossible to visually isolate just those selected hair cells in the confocal image. Very commonly, additional hair cells appear in the fore- or background and overlap wholly or partly with the selected ones. This illustrates the power of the image analysis used, in isolating individual hair cells and allocating individual ribbons to them. Note also that some of the confocal images are not simple Z-projections but were virtually rotated if necessary, to achieve an approximately perpendicular view onto the hair cells' long axes. Only panels F and G provide a more oblique view, in order to reveal two selected hair cells that overlapped completely in a perpendicular view. Immunolabels are: Myosin VIIa label of hair cells, shown gray; CtBP2 label of presynaptic ribbons, magenta; synapsin label of efferent terminals, cyan. The magenta and cyan channels were subjected to deconvolution (see Section 2.3), and brightness and contrast of all labels were further adjusted for the final figure

significance criterion was set at $p \leq .01$. Nonparametric statistics were preferentially used; specifically Kruskal–Wallis multisample and subsequent pairwise Mann–Whitney U tests. In the case of multiple post-hoc comparisons, a Bonferroni adjustment of the criterion p value was applied, dividing 0.01 by the number of pairwise tests required. Statistics were supplemented by parametric analyses of variance (ANOVA), to test for the effects of several factors and their interaction. To account for repeated measurements (multiple hair cells) from the same subject, a mixed-model design, with the individual animal as a subject factor, was used. The assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variances were judged using both descriptive plots and standard tests (Kolmogorov–Smirnov, Levene). Dependent variables were log-transformed, as this considerably improved compliance with the assumptions in all cases. However, we note that the data never completely satisfied all assumptions.

3 | RESULTS

We characterized synapse development in the chicken BP by focusing first on the number of presynaptic ribbons per hair cell, and second on the relative volume of those ribbons. Both parameters were quantified for normal developmental conditions, and then in comparison to development influenced by excessive Wnt9a.

Our investigation covered the developmental periods of the differentiation of the hair-cell types and their innervation, beginning at E12 and sampling further embryonic stages E14, E16, and E18. We chose to begin at E12 for two reasons: Firstly, because we were most interested in the synaptogenesis at the time when the two hair cell types have become distinct. By E12, the different hair cell phenotypes have been unambiguously produced (Cohen and Fermin, 1978). Secondly, because the time window E11–13 was earlier described as mid-synaptogenesis, which in turn was characterised by most prominent changes in the number of synaptic bodies (Whitehead & Morest, 1985b). The mature status was represented by P21. Ribbons were analyzed in wholemount BP preparations of 11 untreated control ears and of 11 ears from the same specimens with Wnt9a overexpression. Thus, the untreated ears contralateral to the experimental ears of the same individuals served as controls. In every BP, four sample areas were selected and from each of those, typically 6 (5–10, see Supporting information Table S1) hair cells were analyzed. The sample areas were located at two cross-sectional locations (neural, THC domain, and abneural, SHC domain), and at two longitudinal locations (10 and 50% from the basal end of the BP; overview in Figure 1A), corresponding to characteristic frequencies (CF) of 5.5 and 1 kHz, respectively (Chen et al., 1994). More apical locations were deliberately excluded, because this part of the BP naturally contains mainly THC. According to morphological

criteria summarized in the introduction (cell-body shape and innervation), SHC can only be found naturally in the basal two-thirds of the chicken BP (Fischer, 1994a). Thus, the BP's apex is less suitable for a comparison of THC versus SHC development, or of its perturbation by Wnt9a overexpression.

3.1 | Normal development

3.1.1 | Number of ribbons/hair cell showed developmental changes in the THC, but not in the SHC domain

Since very few quantitative data are available for ribbon numbers in hair cells of the chicken BP, we first clarified whether there were any systematic variations across our different sampling sites in mature control BP. A linear mixed-model ANOVA suggested that in P21 control ears, the number of ribbons/hair cell varied significantly across but not along the BP (fixed factor longitudinal location: $F = 4.7$, $p = .035$, fixed factor cross-sectional location: $F = 9.9$, $p = .003$). Adding age as a further fixed factor to the mixed model showed a highly significant influence ($F = 8.3$, $p < .001$) that also interacted significantly with cross-sectional location ($F = 3.5$, $p = .008$), suggesting developmental changes in ribbon numbers, with a differential change at neural and abneural locations. Post-hoc tests revealed that only hair cells situated at the neural edge of the BP showed significant changes in their numbers of ribbons over the different stages investigated (Figure 2A, left panels; K-W test, $p = .002$), but not hair cells situated at the abneural edge (Figure 2A, right panels; K-W test, $p = .011$). Having established the principal effects of cross-sectional papillar location and age, the following paragraphs explore in more detail the developmental time course of changes in ribbon numbers.

At the neural edge, there was an early increase in the number of ribbons/hair cell from E12 to E14. At the 50% longitudinal location, the number of ribbons nearly doubled, from a median number of 12 ribbons/hair cell at E12, to 21 at E14 (Figure 2A, top left panel; descriptive statistics for all stages and sampling locations are provided in Supporting information Table S1). As development progressed, a decrease in the number of ribbons/hair cell towards the mature condition was observed at both longitudinal BP locations. This decrease, however, occurred at different stages of development. At the 10% longitudinal location, the numbers fell after E14 (Figure 2A, bottom left panel), whereas at the 50% longitudinal location, this happened somewhat later, after E16 (Figure 2A, top left panel).

A comparison of ribbon numbers across the BP revealed that in the youngest embryonic stage investigated, E12, the number of ribbons was higher in hair cells located in the neural THC domain, compared to abneurally located hair cells (Figure 3A). This was true for both longitudinal BP locations,

FIGURE 2 Number of presynaptic ribbons/hair cell at different developmental stages, for each of the four BP sampling locations. (A) Data for control ears, shown in shades of blue. (B) Data for Wnt9a-overexpressing ears, shown in shades of red. Note that the color coding is consistent throughout Figures 2–4, and the Supporting information. Each panel is further subdivided into four boxplot graphs each, representing the four BP locations evaluated: 50% neural and 50% abneural in the upper row, and 10% neural and 10% abneural in the lower row. Each boxplot illustrates the number of ribbons/hair cell, as a function of developmental stage, from E12 to P21; later stages are coded by increasingly darker shades of color, as defined by the legend. For each embryonic stage, two ears were evaluated, and three ears for P21; six hair cells from each ear were typically evaluated for each sampled location, that is, 12 (or 18 for P21) hair cells in total (see Supporting information Table S1 for precise sample sizes). Boxes indicate medians (thick horizontal line) and interquartile ranges, whiskers indicate 1.5 times the interquartile range, outliers beyond that are shown as circles ($>1.5 < 3$ times interquartile range) and coloured asterisks (>3 times interquartile range). Solid lines join the median values, to graphically emphasize the development of ribbon number across stages. Black asterisks above the boxes indicate statistically significant differences between pairs of developmental stages indicated by brackets (Mann–Whitney U test), $^{**}.01 \geq p > .001$, $^{***}p \leq .001$

10 and 50%. At the 50% longitudinal location, this higher number of ribbons in neurally located hair cells was sustained during all stages of development (Figure 3A, top row of panels). In contrast, at the 10% longitudinal location, this difference disappeared at E14 and ribbon number/hair cell remained similar between neurally and abneurally located hair cells at all later stages (Figure 3A, bottom row of panels).

It is clear from the above observations that low numbers of presynaptic ribbons formed and persisted in abneurally located SHC despite the fact that these typically do not receive afferent innervation in the mature BP (Fischer, 1992). At the 10% longitudinal location, these numbers were eventually (P21) even indistinguishable in SHC and THC. We note, however, that ribbons in the SHC domain tended to distribute broadly within hair cells and were regularly observed at locations far from the basal pole of the hair cell where afferent terminals typically connect (examples in Figure 1D and H).

3.1.2 | Ribbon volume differed systematically between hair cells, both along and across the BP, in the adult condition

The analysis of the volume of ribbons revealed that ribbons varied in relative size in the mature BP (P21), and there was

a systematic difference between most of the sample areas. Note that ribbon volumes were normalized (see Section 2.3), which precluded multifactorial statistical comparisons across different ears and developmental stages. Ribbons smaller than the median result in normalized values below 1, and ribbons larger than the median in values above 1 (open-ended scale).

Normalization of the ribbon volume within locations covering the same cross-sectional location (neural or abneural, see Section 2.3) permitted relative comparisons between different longitudinal (tonotopic) locations in a given ear. Here, relative ribbon size revealed no clear developmental pattern. Although significant differences were found for some developmental stages, these appeared erratic and followed no clear developmental sequence (Supporting information Figure S1A). However, there was an overall tendency that if differences were observed, the volumes of ribbons at the 10% longitudinal location (~ 5.5 kHz) were more often significantly larger than those in hair cells at the 50% location (~ 1 kHz). This difference also persisted into the mature P21 stage. Furthermore, the difference in ribbon volume was larger for neurally located hair cells (Figure 4A, left panels).

Normalizing the volume of ribbons within the two cross-sectional locations allowed us to compare between neurally and abneurally located hair cells of the same longitudinal (tonotopic) location in a given ear. Here, too, no clear

FIGURE 3 Number of presynaptic ribbons/hair cell, contrasted between neurally located THC and abneurally located SHC, for each developmental stage. (A) Data for control ears, shown in shades of blue. (B) Data for Wnt9a-overexpressing ears, shown in shades of red. Each panel is further subdivided into two rows of boxplot graphs, representing the two longitudinal BP locations evaluated (50, 10%) and five columns of boxplots, representing the different stages evaluated, from E12 to P21. Individual boxplots contrast the numbers of ribbons/hair cell for neurally located THC and abneurally located SHC. For each embryonic stage, two ears were evaluated, and three ears for P21; six hair cells from each ear were typically evaluated for each sampled location, that is, 12 (or 18 for P21) hair cells in total (see Supporting information Table S1 for precise sample sizes). Boxes indicate medians (thick horizontal line) and interquartile ranges, whiskers indicate 1.5 times the interquartile range, outliers beyond that are shown as circles ($>1.5 < 3$ times interquartile range) and coloured asterisks (>3 times interquartile range). Black asterisks above the boxes indicate statistically significant differences between neurally located THC and abneurally located SHC (Mann–Whitney U test), $** .01 \geq p > .001$, $*** p \leq .001$

sequence of development could be discerned (Supporting information Figure S2A). Ribbon volumes were significantly larger in abneurally located hair cells at some developmental stages, but this again appeared erratic and followed no pattern. In the P21 mature BP, the difference then reversed at the 10% longitudinal location, such that ribbons of neural THC were

FIGURE 4 Normalized volume of presynaptic ribbons in the mature BP (at P21), contrasted between neurally located THC and abneurally located SHC (A) or between the two longitudinal (tonotopic) locations evaluated (B). Each panel is further subdivided into two columns of boxplot graphs, representing data from control ears, shown in blue, and from Wnt9a-overexpressing ears, shown in red. Three ears were evaluated for each condition, and ribbons from six hair cells from each ear were typically evaluated for each sampled location, that is, from 18 hair cells (see Supporting information Table S1 for precise sample sizes). Dashed lines indicate a normalized value of 1, that is, median ribbon volume across both data sets from an individual ear, for reference. (A) Each boxplot compares the normalized ribbon volumes for neurally located THC and abneurally located SHC. (B) Each boxplot compares the normalized ribbon volumes for hair cells located at the 50 and 10% longitudinal positions, equivalent to 1 and 5.5 kHz, respectively. Boxes indicate medians (horizontal line) and interquartile ranges, whiskers indicate 1.5 times the interquartile range, outliers beyond that are shown as circles ($>1.5 < 3$ times interquartile range) and coloured asterisks (>3 times interquartile range). Large black asterisks above the boxes indicate statistically significant differences (Mann–Whitney U test), $** .01 \geq p > .001$, $*** p \leq .001$

significantly larger than those of abneural SHC. No difference was observed at the 50% longitudinal location for mature hair cells (Figure 4B, left panels).

In summary, our data suggest that ribbon volume typically varies along the mature BP, with larger ribbons at the 10% longitudinal location (compared to 50%), for both THC and SHC, albeit a more pronounced difference for THC. When this difference arises during development remained unclear. In the mature BP, larger ribbons may also be typical for neural THC (compared to abneural SHC) at very basal longitudinal location (10%). However, that difference was not observed at any preceding developmental stage.

3.2 | Development under the influence of excessive Wnt9a expression

3.2.1 | Number of ribbons/hair cell showed developmental changes in all hair cells, similar to control THC

Initially, we asked whether Wnt9a overexpression had any effect on ribbon numbers/hair cell. To answer this, we performed a mixed-model ANOVA, entering age, treatment (control or Wnt9a overexpression), and both spatial axes of the BP as fixed factors. This revealed treatment as a highly significant factor ($F = 37.2$, $p < .001$), in addition to age ($F = 26.0$, $p < .001$), and cross-sectional location ($F = 98.3$, $p < .001$). Similarly to observations on control ears alone, ribbon numbers did not vary significantly with longitudinal location ($p = .087$). Interestingly, only two significant interactions of factors were found: between treatment and age ($F = 7.7$, $p < .001$), and treatment and cross-sectional location ($F = 6.8$, $p = .009$), suggesting different development of ribbon numbers in control and Wnt9a overexpressing ears (Wnt9a-OE), with a differential change at neural and abneural positions. This prompted us to explore in more detail the development in Wnt9a-OE ears. Below, we highlight the changes relative to the normal development of ribbon numbers characterized above.

The number of ribbons/hair cell in the Wnt9a-OE ears showed a significant decrease during development in all four BP sample locations: 10% neural (K-W test, $p < .001$), 10% abneural (K-W test, $p < .001$), 50% neural (K-W test, $p < .001$), and 50% abneural (K-W test, $p = .005$; note: stages E12 and E14 were not included in the K-W test here, due to the lack of data; see Section 2.3 and Supporting information Table S1).

At the neural cross-sectional locations, the numbers continuously fell from the initially (at E12) observed highest values of 18 (at 10% longitudinal) and 26 ribbons/hair cell (at 50% longitudinal) (Figure 2B, left panels). As a result, in the mature condition (P21), the number of ribbons/hair cell was

then as low as 5 ribbons/hair cell at the 10% longitudinal location, and 6 at the 50% longitudinal location (Figure 2B, left panels and Supporting information Table S1). For neurally located hair cells, there was, thus, no principal difference between developing control ears and Wnt9a-OE ears, except for subtle changes in the time course (see next section 3.2.2).

Abneural BP locations differed more clearly in their development between control ears and Wnt9a-OE ears. In contrast to the stable, low number of ribbons in controls, the abneural locations of Wnt9a-OE ears tended to show higher numbers at early developmental stages and then exhibited a significant decrease toward the mature condition, after E16 (Figure 2B, right panels). This indicates that during development, the abneural side of the Wnt9a-OE BP did not display the typical features of an SHC domain.

In summary, during most of their development, hair cells from the abneural side of Wnt9a-OE ears expressed a phenotype consistent with a THC domain, forming an ectopic THC domain at abneural locations.

3.2.2 | Developmental time course of ribbon numbers was altered

At neural locations, while with advancing development Wnt9a-OE ears exhibited a similar principal decrease in ribbon numbers as did control ears, the time course of that decrease was subtly altered. In Wnt9a-OE ears, the maximal number of ribbons/hair cell was already evident at the youngest stage investigated, E12, and did not significantly decrease until after E16 (at the 10% longitudinal location, Figure 2B, bottom left panel), or even E18 (at the 50% longitudinal location, Figure 2B, top left panel). Hair cells at the neural edge, thus, experienced an extended phase of high ribbon numbers. Compared to controls, their ribbon numbers tended to be higher at earlier stages and declined at later stages.

The late decline of ribbon numbers in neurally located hair cells in Wnt9a-OE ears, after E16, was mirrored by abneurally located hair cells (Figure 2B, right panels). A prolonged peak in ribbon numbers, from the earliest stage, was only evident for the 10% longitudinal location—but note the insufficient sample size for the 50% location (Figure 2B, right panels). Together, this provides further support for abnormal THC-domain-like behaviour in the SHC domain, even to the extent of showing the same altered time course of ribbon development under the influence of excessive Wnt9a.

Despite the major alteration of ribbon development in the abneural SHC domain under Wnt9a overexpression, resembling development of neural THC, the principal pattern of relative ribbon numbers in neurally versus abneurally located hair cells was preserved over much of the development. In control ears, through all ages investigated, hair cells of the 50% longitudinal location showed a significantly higher

number of ribbons/hair cell in the neural THC domain compared with the abneural domain (Figure 3A, top row of panels). This difference was largely maintained at the 50% longitudinal location of Wnt9a-OE ears, with the interesting exception of the mature (P21) stage (see next section 3.2.3). At the 10% longitudinal location, control ears showed a difference in ribbon numbers for neurally and abneurally located hair cells only very early in development, at E12, but at no further stages (Figure 3A, bottom row of panels). Similarly, Wnt9a-OE ears revealed no significant differences at any developmental stage (Figure 3B, bottom row of panels).

3.2.3 | Abnormal ribbon numbers of abneurally located hair cells were transient and did not persist into the mature condition

As shown above, during development, the number of ribbons in abneurally located hair cells of Wnt9a-OE ears changed at both longitudinal locations, in contrast to controls, where it did not vary, but remained low in the abneural SHC domain. In the mature-stage P21, ribbon numbers finally fell to control levels at abneural locations of the Wnt9a-OE ears: Hair cells then contained a median of 6.5 ribbons in controls and 4.5 ribbons in Wnt9a-OE ears at the 10% longitudinal location (M-W test between control and Wnt9a-OE ears, $p = .014$), and 5.0 ribbons in controls and 5.5 ribbons in Wnt9a-OE ears at the 50% longitudinal location (M-W test, $p = .314$). Similarly, at the neural edge of mature-stage Wnt9a-OE ears, ribbon numbers decreased down to (at the 10% longitudinal location), or even below (at the 50% longitudinal location), control levels (Figure 2A and B; M-W test for 10% location, $p = .125$; for 50% location, $p = .008$).

3.2.4 | Differences in relative ribbon volume were subtly altered in mature-stage Wnt9a-OE ears

The above analysis showed that, with respect to ribbon numbers, Wnt9a overexpression in abneurally located hair cells during development induced a phenotype more similar to THC, and less like typical SHC. However, by P21, the number of ribbons/hair cell had decreased to control levels. This raised the question whether this late return to control conditions also held with respect to ribbon volume. A comparison of relative ribbon volume between hair cells at the two cross-sectional locations (neural vs. abneural) revealed no coherent pattern during development, and thus resembled the development in controls (Supporting information Figure S2).

In the mature-stage (P21) Wnt9a-OE ears, there was no difference in the relative volume of ribbons between neural and abneural locations at either longitudinal location (Figure 4B, right panels). This was similar to observations at the 50% longitudinal location in controls, but was in contrast to the 10%

longitudinal location of control ears, where neural THC and abneural SHC differed significantly in their ribbon volumes (Figure 4B, bottom left panel). This difference was lost in the basal Wnt9a-OE BP (Figure 4B, bottom right panel).

Differences in ribbon volume between hair cells at the two longitudinal locations (10 and 50%) were present in mature Wnt9a-OE, and were in the same direction as those observed in control ears (Figure 4A). However, a clear developmental pattern leading to this difference was not evident, again similar to control ears (Supporting information Figure S1B).

In summary, the characteristic mature situation of longitudinal location-dependent relative ribbon volumes was not altered in Wnt9a-OE ears. However, the subtle difference in ribbon volumes between THC and SHC seen in mature control ears for the 10% longitudinal location, was abolished.

4 | DISCUSSION

The development of the innervation of the chicken inner ear was studied in detail in the late 1970s and early 1980s (Cohen & Fermin, 1978, 1985; Fermin & Cohen, 1984; Hirokawa, 1978a; Rebillard & Pujol, 1983; Whitehead & Morest, 1985a,b). The focus of their research was the developmental sequence of afferent and efferent terminals and hair-cell formation, with less attention to ribbon development. Presynaptic ribbons of afferent synapses are formed between E8 and E12 (Cohen & Fermin, 1978; Fermin & Cohen, 1984; Hirokawa, 1978a; Levic et al., 2011; Rebillard & Pujol, 1983; Whitehead & Morest, 1985a,b) and the synapses change until the mature condition is achieved. The auditory organ of the chicken is mostly mature at two to three weeks after hatching: the cochlear duct has almost reached its adult size (Ryals et al., 1984), the impedance to sound transfer from air to cochlea through the middle ear has decreased compared to late embryos and hatchlings (Jones et al., 2006), cochlear sensitivity and auditory-nerve fiber characteristics mature in the first few weeks (Jones et al., 2006; Manley et al., 1991), and the hair-cell bundles acquire the mature orientation at P3 in the whole BP (Cotanche & Corwin, 1991).

At the time when many of the classic studies were carried out, quantitative assessments of many cochlear locations were difficult, with transmission electron microscopy on ultrathin sections being the dominant technique. In addition, the longitudinal (tonotopic) locations of the chicken auditory organ that were evaluated were not always specified, which is unfortunate, as it is now clear that developmental gradients along the BP exist. Since then, improvements in confocal light microscopy have made it more feasible to acquire larger data samples. Studies such as ours, of presynaptic ribbons at several, defined papillar locations and across several stages of development, complement the classic work, and provide more insights into the overall development of the chicken BP.

FIGURE 5 Schematic summary of normal ribbon development (A) and development under the influence of Wnt9a-OE (B). Each panel illustrates three salient stages of development (early, intermediate, mature; from left to right). For each stage, four typical hair cells, with typical relative numbers and relative volumes of presynaptic ribbons, are shown: a neurally located (future) THC and an abneurally located (future) SHC, separately for the two longitudinal (tonotopic) locations evaluated here. It is important to realize that the relative ribbon sizes are only meaningful between hair cells of a given stage. Therefore, the illustration does *not* imply that ribbons increased in size in the mature state, relative to earlier developmental stages. Normal development was characterized by a transient overshoot of ribbon numbers in the neural THC domain, while fewer ribbons formed in the abneural SHC domain and their number persisted unchanged into the mature condition. Wnt9a overexposure caused a transient, increased formation of ribbons, most prominently in the SHC domain, and a subtle delay of the time course of reduction in ribbon numbers towards the location-typical mature levels. Ribbon volumes varied between mature hair cells from different longitudinal (tonotopic) locations, being larger in both THC and SHC of more basal, high-frequency locations. This was not affected by Wnt9a-OE

Here, we describe a large part of the normal timeline of ribbon development along two dimensions of the chicken's BP, from shortly after the first ribbons appear to the mature condition (P21). Figure 5 summarizes the main findings in a simple schematic. Normal development was characterized by a transient overshoot of ribbon numbers in the neural THC domain, while fewer ribbons formed in the abneural SHC domain and their number persisted unchanged into the mature condition. Wnt9a overexposure caused a transient, increased formation of ribbons, most prominently in the SHC domain, and a subtle delay of the time course of reduction in ribbon numbers towards the location-typical mature levels. Ribbon volumes varied between mature hair cells from different longitudinal (tonotopic) locations, being larger in both THC and SHC of more basal, high-frequency locations. This was not affected by Wnt9a-OE.

4.1 | Tonotopic gradients in development

At the neural edge of the BP, where the future THC are situated, our study revealed that the number of ribbons temporarily increased at the 50% (1 kHz) location of the BP, between

E12 and E14. In contrast, in the basal (5.5 kHz) area, the number of ribbons was stable and high during that time. This could indicate that the basal area experienced the same increase at earlier stages that were not studied here. Supporting this interpretation, the subsequent decrease in ribbon numbers began earlier at the basal position, after E14, compared to the middle position, where the decrease started after E16. Our results are thus consistent with a base-to-apex developmental gradient in the chicken BP, as previously found (Cohen & Fermin, 1978; Cotanche & Corwin, 1991; Fermin & Cohen, 1984). Ribbon numbers in hair cells at more apical, low-frequency locations would then be expected to develop even later, consistent with the observations of Levic et al. (2011), who, for hair cells in the most apical one third, reported an increase in ribbon numbers as late as P2.

The decrease we observed in ribbon counts in THC coincided in time with the onset of afferent responses to ambient sound (around E16; Jones et al., 2006). Similarly, during mammalian development, ribbon numbers of IHC decrease around P12, coinciding with the onset of hearing in the mouse (Lieberman & Liberman, 2016; Michanski et al., 2019; Sobkowicz et al., 1982, 1986; Wong et al., 2014) and the rat (Kalluri & Monges-Hernandez, 2017). This suggests that a

reduction of ribbon numbers is one manifestation of synapse refinement in THC and IHC.

4.2 | Orphaned ribbons and their development in short hair cells

As defined by Fischer (1992), mature THC are innervated by afferent fibers while mature SHC are not. These two types of hair cells are distributed differentially along and across the chicken hearing organ: THC predominate at the apical neural edge and SHC at the basal abneural edge. The afferent synaptic contact area roughly follows the same decreasing pattern from apical to basal and from neural to abneural (Fischer, 1992). Since presynaptic ribbons are involved in afferent transmission, no ribbons are expected in SHC. However, it was previously observed that SHC do contain ribbons, albeit in sometimes unexpected locations, for example, facing efferent terminals, which suggests they are functional orphans without a postsynaptic partner (Fischer, 1992; Tanaka & Smith, 1978). The number of ribbons decreases from neural to abneural hair cells across the width of the BP, with a more pronounced decrease at the 50% longitudinal location, compared to more apical locations (Martinez-Dunst et al., 1997). This closely mirrors the innervation pattern of diminishing afferent contacts as quantified by Fischer (1992). Here, we show that at very basal longitudinal locations (our 10%), mature THC also contain very low numbers of ribbons. This is again consistent with Fischer's (1992) innervation data for THC at such basal locations, and suggests these are indeed functional presynaptic elements while the SHC ribbons in our mature control ears are likely functional orphans.

Furthermore, the development of ribbons in THC and SHC clearly differed in our data, such that only neurally located THC experienced a change in the number of ribbons/hair cell, while ribbon numbers in abneurally located SHC remained constantly low. This may be related to the fact that mature, abneurally located hair cells at the longitudinal (tonotopic) positions studied here typically do not form functional synapses with postsynaptic afferent fibers (Fischer, 1992). Thus, ribbon-synapse maturation might not occur in hair cells that lack afferent innervation, in agreement with previous findings that afferent innervation is important for synapse refinement and maintenance, but not for ribbon formation (Flock & Russell, 1973; Sheets et al., 2012; Sobkowicz et al., 1986; Suli et al., 2016).

There are other examples of mature hair cells that lack afferent innervation and yet harbor synaptic ribbons (Chiappe et al., 2007); to our knowledge, however, their development has not been investigated. The fact that synaptic ribbons without an apparent function persist in these hair cells is an interesting observation in itself. Despite an often-cited analogy between avian SHC and mammalian OHC (e.g., Köppl,

2011), compared to OHC the more extreme, complete lack of afferent innervation in SHC appears to be associated with profound differences in ribbon development and maintenance. In the mammalian cochlea, synaptic ribbons appear in both IHC and OHC (Kalluri & Monges-Hernandez, 2017; Liberman & Liberman, 2016; Sobkowicz et al., 1982, 1986), analogous to our observations in both THC and SHC. However, in contrast to birds, in which ribbon numbers in SHC remain stable, ribbon numbers in OHC drastically decrease around P10 (Kalluri & Monges-Hernandez, 2017; Liberman & Liberman, 2016; Sobkowicz et al., 1982, 1986). This decrease in OHC ribbon numbers coincides with a period of afferent reorganization and neurite retraction of type-I auditory-nerve fibers from OHC, followed by the establishment of type-II afferent contacts (reviewed in Groves & Fekete, 2017). Developing avian SHC may also undergo a transient liaison with afferent terminals (Rebillard & Pujol, 1983), but it remains unclear whether functional synapses ever form.

4.3 | Tonotopic variations in ribbon volume

In the mature BP, our evaluation of relative ribbon volume suggested that it is tonotopically dependent, as previously observed by Martinez-Dunst et al. (1997), who assessed ribbon size more directly and precisely in electron microscopic material. They found that ribbons in hair cells located 2 mm from the apex (comparable to our 50% longitudinal location) had a greater diameter than ribbons from hair cells located more apically, at 1 and 0.3 mm from the apex. Furthermore, Martinez-Dunst et al. (1997) found no difference in size between ribbons in neurally and abneurally located hair cells. Therefore, we expected no differences in ribbon size between the hair cell types (THC and SHC) in our samples. This was true for the 50% longitudinal location, but surprisingly not for the 10% position, where ribbons in neurally located hair cells were relatively larger than ribbons in abneurally located hair cells. Together, these data suggest that ribbon size varies predominantly along the tonotopic axis, with larger ribbons in hair cells sensitive to higher frequencies. In contrast, ribbon size appears to be largely independent of hair cell type (neural THC or abneural SHC), perhaps with the exception of the very basal positions, that is, THC and SHC near the high-frequency limit.

The functional consequences of tonotopic variations in ribbon size are an interesting question. Abnormally large ribbons in zebrafish lateral-line hair cells have more vesicles tethered to the ribbon, but their exocytosis in response to voltage steps was not greater than from normal ribbons, indicating that the number of synaptic vesicles released is not affected by the size of the ribbon (Sheets et al., 2017). At synapses with such enlarged ribbons, calcium channels are less densely clustered and the hair cells have larger calcium influx currents, but the

postsynaptic densities opposing those larger ribbons are not altered (Sheets et al., 2017). In chickens, it has been suggested that the size of the release area (calculated as the area of the cell membrane immediately under the ribbon) correlates with an increase of calcium influx currents (Martinez-Dunst et al., 1997). In the mammalian cochlea, synapses with naturally larger ribbons contain higher numbers of voltage-gated calcium channels, associated with a larger local Ca^{2+} influx (Ohn et al., 2016). This indicates that the positive correlation between the size of the active zone and the calcium influx is consistent across species. In mammals, larger ribbons located on the modiolar side of IHC are associated with afferent fibers characterized by low spontaneous rates and high acoustic thresholds (Merchan-Perez & Liberman, 1996). The calcium channels associated with ribbons from the modiolar side of IHC operate at relatively more positive potentials, requiring more depolarization for their activation. The smaller ribbons on the pillar side of the same IHC operate at more negative potentials, which should lead to more spontaneous firing at the IHC resting potential in-vivo (Ohn et al., 2016).

Together, this reinforces the idea suggested by Martinez-Dunst et al. (1997), that the tonotopic organization of ribbon size, with larger ribbons in hair cell at higher-frequency locations, might also affect the number and organization of calcium channels in a tonotopic manner. If, as in mammalian IHC, the environment created at these larger ribbons influences the opening probability of the calcium channels, by requiring more depolarization to activate them, this would predict lower spontaneous rates and higher thresholds in afferent fibers with increasing frequencies in the chicken BP. Indeed, decreased spontaneous activity with increasing CF is typical for mature avian auditory-nerve fibers (Klinke et al., 1994; Köppl, 1997; Manley et al., 1985; Richter et al., 1996), but not a concomitant, overall decline in sensitivity with increasing CF.

Further studies are required to determine the number, organization, and opening probabilities of calcium channels and the properties of afferent fibers associated with smaller ribbons at low-frequency locations and larger ribbons at high-frequency locations, respectively, to clarify causal relationships.

4.4 | Influence of excessive Wnt9a-OE during development

The underlying mechanisms that establish the THC-SHC gradation along and across the avian BP are not fully understood. Munnamalai et al. (2017) provided evidence that the Wnt/ β -catenin ligand Wnt9a might play an important role in establishing these two cell fates across the radial axis (neural-abneural) of the BP. When they analyzed the Wnt9a-OE ears more closely, they found that both neural and abneural hair

cells had an increased number of ribbons compared to controls. At E18, abneurally located cells displayed a THC-like phenotype regarding hair cell shape and efferent innervation, but outward ion currents that were reminiscent of SHC (Munnamalai et al., 2017).

The present study used the same Wnt9a-OE model to replicate the results of Munnamalai et al. (2017) and investigate the phenotype of individual hair cells with respect to both ribbon number and volume. In addition, we extended the analysis into a more complete developmental sequence including earlier stages (E12, E14, and E16). Finally, our analysis also included the mature (P21) condition, to explore whether the developmental changes persist into the adult, and to assess the suitability of this animal model for future physiological studies.

At all BP locations evaluated, Wnt9a-OE ears showed decreasing numbers of ribbons/hair cell with advancing development. In the neural domain, this decrease began earlier at the basal (10% longitudinal) location, compared to the 50% longitudinal location. This indicates that the base-to-apex developmental gradient of hair-cell differentiation was still present, and was, thus, not principally affected by the overexpression of Wnt9a. However, the decrease in ribbon numbers was delayed when compared with control ears. A delayed development in Wnt9a-OE was already suggested by Munnamalai et al. (2017) who observed a 2- to 3-day lag in hair-cell differentiation. This delay in the development of Wnt9a-OE now puts the increased ribbon numbers observed by Munnamalai et al. (2017) at E18 in neurally located hair cells in context. At that stage, control ears have already decreased their ribbon counts to the adult condition, while the Wnt9a-OE ears have yet not achieved that stage (compare Figure 2A and B).

The decrease after E16—also on the abneural side of the Wnt9a-OE ears—clearly contrasted with the stable ribbon numbers in abneurally located hair cells of controls. Instead, this decrease resembles the development of ribbon numbers in neurally located hair cells from Wnt9a-OE and reinforces the conclusion (Munnamalai et al., 2017) that abneurally located hair cells express a THC-like phenotype in developing Wnt9a-OE. Under the influence of excessive Wnt9a, the normal SHC phenotype is absent during development.

However, our analysis of the adult (P21) BP revealed that ribbon numbers in Wnt9a-OE decreased to control levels, or even below, in hair cells at all locations studied. This indicates that the high number of ribbons observed in both control and Wnt9a-OE ears in neurally located hair cells, as well as in abneurally located hair cells of Wnt9a-OE ears, is a transient phenomenon until hair cells finally commit to a mature status.

A possible reason for the final decrease to near-normal ribbon numbers in Wnt9a-OE ears could be a loss of Wnt9a overexpression over time, which we did not assess. However, note that the number of ribbons/hair cell in Wnt9a-OE ears fell to control levels or even below at P21. We argue that this

in fact might indicate a sustained influence and bioactivity of Wnt misexpression in the post-hatching inner ear, which makes this model attractive for investigating the mechanisms by which Wnt signaling mediates the developmental changes in synaptic numbers. It might also indicate a possible transition to synaptic plasticity being governed by neuronal activity in the auditory system. A growing body of literature now demonstrates that Wnts not only regulate synapse formation, but also promote the remodeling of mature terminals elicited by changes in electrical activity and environmental experience (reviewed by Budnik & Salinas, 2011). The more recently reported requirement of Wnt activity for synapse integrity in the adult hippocampus highlights the role of Wnt signaling beyond development and into the mature system, and the vulnerability of synapses under conditions of deficient Wnt signaling, which is also relevant to human disorders (Marzo et al., 2016).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge the Fluorescence Microscopy Service Unit, Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg, for the use of the imaging facilities. We also thank Dr. Lena Köpcke for programming support with image analysis. Supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (Grants KO 1143/15-1 to CK and SI 823/3-1 to UJS). English language services were provided by www.stels-ol.de.

Open access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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How to cite this article: Caus Capdevila, M. Q., Sienknecht, U. J., & Köppl, C. (2021). Developmental maturation of presynaptic ribbon numbers in chicken basilar-papilla hair cells and its perturbation by long-term overexpression of Wnt9a. *Developmental Neurobiology*, *81*, 817–832.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/dneu.22845>